

Computation of Geometric Series on Relation between Dirichlet Eta Function and Riemann Zeta Function

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Abstract: This paper presents a technique to computer a geometric series from the relationship between the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann Zeta function.

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1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-16] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and also in the summation of series involving the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function [17-19]. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [20].

2. Novel Technique for Sum of Geometric Series

Theorem 2.1:
$$\sum_{k=2}^n \frac{1}{2^{k-1}} = \frac{2^{n-1} - 1}{2^{n-1}}.$$

Proof. Let us proof this theorem using $1 = 1$.

$$1 = 1 \Rightarrow 1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4} \Rightarrow 1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^2}$$

We can continue this process up to $(n - 1)$.

$$1 = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^3} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{1}{2^{n-1}}. \quad (1)$$

From the equation (1), we conclude that

$$1 - \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^3} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \Rightarrow \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{1}{2^{k-1}} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} = \frac{2^{n-1} - 1}{2^{n-1}}. \quad (2)$$

Hence proved.

3. Geometric Series with Dirichlet Eta Function and Riemann Zeta Function

The Riemann zeta function is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots$$

The Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $\Re(s) > 1$.

The Dirichlet eta function is defined by

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} - \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots$$

The Dirichlet eta function $\eta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $Re(s) > 0$.

Theorem 3.1: $\frac{\eta(s)}{\zeta(s)} = \frac{2^{s-1} - 1}{2^{s-1}}$.

Proof. Let prove this theorem as follows:

$$\zeta(s) - \eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} - \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots$$

$$\zeta(s) - \eta(s) = \frac{2}{2^s} + \frac{2}{4^s} + \frac{2}{6^s} + \frac{2}{8^s} + \frac{2}{10^s} + \frac{2}{12^s} + \dots = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)^s} = \frac{2}{2^s} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}$$

$$\zeta(s) - \eta(s) = \frac{1}{2^{s-1}} \zeta(s) \Rightarrow \zeta(s) - \frac{1}{2^{s-1}} \zeta(s) = \eta(s)$$

$$\eta(s) = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{s-1}}\right) \zeta(s) \Rightarrow \frac{\eta(s)}{\zeta(s)} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^{s-1}} = \frac{2^{s-1} - 1}{2^{s-1}}$$

Hence proved.

Now, let us consider s as a positive integer and $s > 1$ in theorem 3.1.

Then, $\frac{\eta(s)}{\zeta(s)} = \frac{2^{s-1} - 1}{2^{s-1}}, \quad s > 1.$ (3)

From the equations (2) and (3), we get

$$\frac{\eta(s)}{\zeta(s)} = \sum_{k=2}^s \frac{1}{2^{k-1}} = \frac{2^{s-1} - 1}{2^{s-1}}.$$
 (4)

Where $\sum_{k=2}^s \frac{1}{2^{k-1}}$ is a geometric series.

4. Conclusion

In the article, the author has constructed a mathematical structure relates a geometric series with the relation between the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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